

Colophospermum mopane

Mopane

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Ranges from small shrubs (3-5m) to tall trees (18-25m) depending on the ecosystem

Distribution:

Colophospermum mopane is widely distributed across southern Africa, extending from the northern parts of South Africa into Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, Malawi, Namibia and Angola.

Importance:

The Mopane tree, indigenous to northern South Africa and endemic to Africa, is the primary host of the Mopane worm, an important traditional protein source. Sequencing its genome provides a foundation for studying population genetic diversity and guiding conservation. It also enables genome annotation and analysis of molecular pathways involved in leaf secondary metabolism, supporting better understanding of Mopane tree and caterpillar ecology.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 153.41 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 5.72 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.81 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 99.2% [Single: 84.3%, Duplicated: 14.9%]
BUSCO database: eukaryota
Assembly N50: 34 688.87 kilobases
Contig number: 6 164

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